

DIPLOMICS' Biodiversity Genomics High Impact High visibility project

SAMPLE SUBMISSION FORM

May 2025

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Instructions

- This form is built in REDCap
- A link to this form is sent to the Sample Contributor if their species nomination is successful.
- By typing their name and submitting the form, the Sample Contributor agrees to the T&Cs of the 1KSA project as set out on the 1KSA website (www.1KSA.org.za).
- * Indicates a compulsory field

1KSA Terms & Conditions

DIPLOMICS is an 'Omics' (Genomics, Proteomics, Metabolomics and Bioinformatics) technology resource for researchers in South Africa and aims to:

1. Create and maintain a world-class infrastructure in South Africa for Omics research.
2. Enable access for students and researchers to Omics technology.

To support these objectives, and to support the generation, analysis and application of good quality Omics data, DIPLOMICS has created the 1KSA high visibility, high impact project, with the aim of sequencing genomes of biodiversity and economic importance in South Africa. This will be accomplished through long-read sequencing using Oxford Nanopore technology for an initial draft genome assembly. DIPLOMICS and its partner labs are recruiting samples for the 1KSA project. As a first step, species nominations are made on the 1KSA website. Following review and approval by the 1KSA steering committee, a REDCap link is sent for on-line completion of this form.

It is important to note that DIPLOMICS is not a funder and that only one sample per species will be supported under 1KSA. Therefore, you may only submit one sample using this form.

By submitting samples for sequencing under the 1KSA project, the Sample Contributor [Principal Investigator] commits to the following:

- To provide high-quality, high-molecular weight DNA and quality control (QC) metrics (the cost of DNA extraction to be borne by the contributor) OR to provide sample tissue for DNA extraction optimization (only if relevant to a method development project and by prior arrangement).

- To provide well curated metadata and copies all sampling permission documents, transportation permits (e.g. Section 20 permits where required) and benefit sharing agreements (where commercialisation is anticipated).
- To give consent to DIPLOMICS to back-up sequencing data with the Data Intensive Research Initiative of South Africa (DIRISA) and for the data to be administered under the guidelines set out by the 1KSA Data Access committee (1KSA-DAC) established by 1KSA. DIPLOMICS will make all the sequencing data and genome assembly outputs available to the Sample Contributor and for a three-year period, the Sample Contributor is free to use and re-analyse this data.
- The Sample Contributor must apply Open Science principles to the dissemination of research results arising from the generation of sequencing data from their samples.
- If you wish to publish research using the raw data, you must upload the data to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC). Your publication must (1) cite this data, (2) make use of the statement acknowledging the 1KSA project, DIPLOMICS, CHPC, DIRISA and the DSTI on the 1KSA website (www.1ksa.org.za) and (3) be checked by the 1KSA-Data Access committee (1KSA-DAC) prior to publication. 1KSA encourages publications in Open Access Journals and the publication of preprints in bioRxiv. The 1KSA-DAC framework on the 1KSA Zenodo community will provide further information.
- If the sample contributor does not publish within the three-year period, the 1KSA project will upload the fastq and fasta files to ENA after three years (pod5 files are currently not accepted by ENA). The sample contributor may motivate to the 1KSA project for a public embargo period on ENA to be applied in particular circumstances.

- The 1KSA-DAC will also evaluate other applications for access to the data (pod5, fastq and fasta) by a sample user. Within three years of sequencing, the sample contributor will be consulted. If the request is approved, it will be under the conditions of a Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) between the 1KSA project and the scientist requesting the data.
- Furthermore, the Sample Contributor confirms that they will acknowledge the 1KSA project, DIPLOMICS, CHPC, DIRISA and the DSTI in all presentations and communications using sequencing data arising from their samples. The acknowledgement statement can be found on the 1KSA website (www.1ksa.org.za)
- The Sample Contributor will comply with all DSTI reporting requests from DIPLOMICS. For example, number of published papers arising from the sequencing project, funding leveraged from the sequencing project for additional research, number of postgraduate students trained using this sequencing data set and other success stories.
- The Sample Contributor gives consent to DIPLOMICS to publicize the generation of sequencing data for their samples. This will be done, for example by means of a species report card published on the 1KSA website or other media channels. DIPLOMICS intends to make the generation of these data *known but protected as necessary*.
- Where possible, if the sample contributed by the Sample Contributor did not originate in a Biodiversity Biobanks South Africa (BBSA) collection, the Sample Contributor will provide a voucher specimen to the relevant biobank. This Accession number will be provided to DIPLOMICS.

- DIPLOMICS acknowledges that draft genome assemblies may lead to the development of commercially exploitable intellectual property. This intellectual property will belong to the Sample Contributor/their institution, and/or the party responsible for generating the IP. However, DIPLOMICS also acknowledges that South Africa's biodiversity belongs to all her people and that the 1KSA project was made possible by funding support from the DSTI through the SARIR programme. From a benefit sharing perspective, an appropriate percentage of royalties arriving from this commercially exploitable intellectual property, as determined on a case-by-case basis, will be contributed to the 1KSA Education Program. The 1KSA Education Program will be set up by DIPLOMICS to promote biodiversity genomics education in South Africa. The Sample Contributor/ or Sample User (or their institutions) must track any commercially exploitable intellectual property arising from the draft genome assembly and honour any future contributions to the 1KSA Education Program.

Contributor Contact Details and Acknowledgement

1. ***Title, name, and surname:** _____
2. ***Affiliation:** _____
3. ***Role:** _____
4. ***Email:** _____
5. ***Address:**

6. ***Is this sample submission and sequencing part of a collaboration?**
 Yes
 No
7. ***Details of collaboration:** _____
8. ***Is there a student working on the project?**
 Yes
 No
9. ***Student name and surname:** _____
10. ***Student's level of study:**
 PhD
 MSc
 Hons
 Undergrad
 Other
11. ***Student's project title:** _____
12. ***Expected date of student graduation:** __ DD-MM-YYY _____
13. ***By typing your name, this constitutes as your electronic signature, you agree to the terms and conditions of 1KSA as listed on the website and above:**

Commented [JK1]: Additional question somewhere: Is this submission important for Biodiversity, the Bioeconomy or both? Is the project expected to produce Intellectual Property requiring safeguarding?

Commented [MOU2R1]: Good question- I will add it after Q30

Commented [MOU3R1]: Trish, see two new questions 31 and 32 in red

14. *Date of signature: __ DD-MM-YYYY__

Sample Submission

Provide the details of the 'best' DNA sample for your species of interest.

If you are submitting DNA for more than one species to 1KSA, email 1KSA@diplomics.org.za to receive a another sample submission link.

15. *To which laboratory will you be submitting your 1KSA sample?

- DIPLOMICS Training Lab (Woodstock)
- UPGL (University Pretoria)
- SAIAB (Makhanda)
- CenGen (Worcester)
- UWC (University of the Western Cape)
- SAMRC Genomics Lab (Parow, Cape Town)

16. *Type of sample submitted:

- Tissue (method development projects only)
- Extracted DNA

17. *Have you acquired all necessary ethical, legal and permitting permissions to submit samples for whole genome sequencing?

- Yes
- No

18. *Please detail all ethical, legal and permitting documentation (including permit numbers etc.) associated with the samples you're submitting:

*Example: Institutional Ethics: XXXX; Collection Permit: XXXX; ToPS: XXXX; CITES: XXXX; Section 20 Permit: XXXX. **NB!** We cannot accept samples without the required ethics / permit documentation*

19. *Whose name is on the permits / ethics documentation? _____

20. *Upload the supporting documentation as one PDF: _____

You may have to zip your files if the size is > 32 MB.

21. *What should the lab do with any remaining sample after completion of the analysis?

- Return to contributor
- Discard

Data Plan

All the sequencing output (raw data and associated run reports) as well as a draft genome assembly will be returned to the sample contributor.

22. ***Do you have a data management plan?**

The data are quite large and need to be handled correctly to ensure integrity. You need to think about where you are going to store these large files and how you are going to work with these data now and in the future.

- Yes
 No

23. ***How would you like to receive the sequencing data? (.pod5 and .fastq files)**

- Via the Centre for High Performance Computing (CHPC) and DIRISA
 On an external hard drive (please provide an external hard drive along with your sample submission)
 Other (please specify below)

24. ***Specify another means of file transfer:** _____

25. ***Do you have a CHPC account?**

- Yes
 No

26. ***Do you have a DIRISA account?**

- Yes
 No

27. ***What is your level of experience with using the command line:**

0 (none) to 10 (experienced)

28. ***Do you acknowledge that 1KSA will run this sequencing data through the draft genome assembly pipeline?**

The 1KSA draft genome assembly pipeline aims to provide a fully collapsed draft genome assembly, with 20x coverage and BUSCO completeness score of 95% or above.

- Yes
 No

29. ***What will be done with the data once you receive it?** _____

Where will you store the data? What analysis will be done and how will you use the draft genome assembly in your research work?? Where will the data be analysed?

30. ***Is this submission important for Biodiversity, the Bioeconomy or both?**

- Bioeconomy
- Biodiversity
- Both

31. ***Is the project expected to produce Intellectual Property requiring safeguarding?**

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

32. ***Would the student on the project need to receive bioinformatics training on genome assembly?**

We plan to conduct a training session once per quarter where students participating in 1KSA can bring their data and we can help troubleshoot, share tips and tricks for genome assembly and using CHPC and DIRISA. If yes, we'll contact you with more information.

- Yes
- No

Species Information

(at the time of sample submission)

33. ***Common name:** _____
This will appear on the species card

34. ***Species name:** _____
Genus and specific epithet. This will appear on the species card

35. ***Do you have a high-quality photograph of the organism for the species card?**
 Yes
 No

If "Yes", please email your photo to information@diplomics.org.za. If "No", please source a high-quality photo of the species and send it to this address.

36. ***Taxon for species card:** _____
Choose the most descriptive.

37. ***Expected genome size:** _____
Genome on a Tree (GoaT) <https://goat.genomehubs.org/>

38. ***Ploidy of species (if known):** _____

39. ***Briefly, in what way is this species important to South African biodiversity?
Why is it important to sequence this genome?** _____
This will appear on the species card

40. ***Species distribution:** _____
This will appear on the species card

41. ***Organism size:** _____
Units and dimension

42. ***Genus:** _____

43. ***Family:** _____

44. ***Order:** _____

45. ***Class:** _____

46. ***Phylum:** _____

47. **(Hidden Field) Taxonomy checked and signed-off via internal QC:**

- Yes
 No

48. **Strain, breed, cultivar, ecotype:** _____

49. **Sex:** _____

50. **Developmental stage:** _____

51. **Specific phenotype:** _____

52. ***Sampling date:** __ DD-MM-YYYY _____

53. ***From which province was the sample sourced?:**

- Eastern Cape
 Free State
 Gauteng
 KwaZulu-Natal
 Limpopo
 Mpumalanga
 Northern Cape
 North-West
 Western Cape

54. ***Sampling location - closest town and/or provincial district?** _____

55. **GPS coordinates (optional):** _____

Latitude and Longitude (degrees). 1KSA will not share the specific sampling location.

56. ***Elevation (terrestrial) OR depth (aquatic):** _____

57. ***Biobank to which the tissue is deposited:**

- SANParks Veterinary Wildlife Services Biobanks
 South African Institute for Aquatic Biodiversity (NRF-SAIAB)
 South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI)
 University of Free State's Department of Microbial, Biochemical and Food Biotechnology
 Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development
 University of Western Cape Institute of Microbial Biotechnology and Metagenomics (IMBM)
 Agricultural Research Council
 None

Other (specify)

58. *Specify which SANBI Biobank:

- Indigenous Plant DNA Biobank
- SANBI Wildlife Biobank
- SANBI Seed Bank

59. *Specify which DALRRD Biobank:

- National Plant Genetic Resources Centre Collection
- The Grootfontein Biobank

60. *Specify which ARC Biobank: _____

61. *Specify "other" biobank / museum / collection:

62. *Voucher number for biobank tissue: _____

Tissue Sample Submission (Method Development Projects Only)

By prior arrangement only

63. *Sample ID: _____
Defined by the contributor

64. *Species: _____

65. *Tissue type: _____

66. *Approximate tissue weight / volume: _____

67. *Detail additive / preservative: _____

68. *Tissue sample storage conditions: _____

DNA Extract Submission

DNA requirements:

- > 1ug of dsDNA as measured by Qubit at a minimum concentration of 100ng/ml,
- Nanodrop A260/A280 ratio = 1.8
- Nanodrop A260/A230 ratio between 2 and 2.2
- Average fragment size > 10kb as measured by TapeStation, gel or equivalent

Quality control disclaimer: If submitted DNA samples do not meet these quality control requirements and these samples do not perform optimally in the assay and application, 1KSA Labs may not be able to proceed with the sequencing reaction, and cannot guarantee the sequencing and/or draft genome assembly outcome.

69. *DNA sample ID: _____

Defined by contributor.

70. *Species: _____

71. *Source of DNA: _____

Blood, saliva, specific tissue

72. *DNA extraction date: _____ DD-MM-YYY _____

73. *DNA extraction method / kit used: _____

Detail any deviations from the manufacturers protocol.

74. *Specify eluate: _____

75. *Specify volume: _____

76. *Qubit concentration: _____

ng /ul

77. *Nanodrop A260 / A280: _____

78. *Nanodrop A260 / A230: _____

79. *Did the sample undergo fragment size analysis?

- Yes
 No

80. *How was the DNA fragment size measured?

- Agarose gel
- TapeStation
- Fragment Analyzer
- LabChip
- Pulse Field Gel Electrophoresis
- Other

81. *Average fragment size (kb): _____

82. *Upload images/ results of the fragment size analysis as one PDF: _____
You may have to zip your files if the size is > 32 MB.

Sample Submission Summary

83. *When will you submit / deliver your sample to the lab? _____

84. Is there anything else you would like the 1KSA project team to know? _____

Please double check that all the information you have provided is correct

SUBMIT

Version History

Version	Date Modified	Significant changes	Changes made by:	Next review date
1.0	15-03-2024	Finalised for Zenodo	P Swart	15-09-2024
2.0	05-09-2024	Corrected typos; added SAMRC GL to list of sample labs; added sample location; provided details about data access & publishing data on ENA.	P Swart and S Murray	05-04-2025
2.1	09-05-2025	Minor corrections, added information about the 1KSA-DAC, included questions about IP and importance of the bioeconomy	P Swart, J Korsmann and S Murray	15-09-2025